

Microteaching Skills as Predictor of Teaching Practice Performance among Business Education Students in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated influence of microteaching skills on teaching practice performance in Business Communication among Business Education students in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria. Correctional research design was adopted. The population comprised 613 final-year Business Education Students across seven Colleges of Education and sample of 613 students who had completed microteaching (EDU 223) and teaching practice (EDU 311). Census sampling technique was adopted because the entire population is manageable. The Cronbach Alpha was adopted to obtain the coefficient index of reliability of questionnaire which yielded 0.70. Findings revealed that microteaching skills influenced teaching practical performance to a high extent. Correlation results revealed that microteaching skills were positively and significantly related to teaching practice performance ($r=0.224$, $p<0.01$). Regression analysis further indicated that lesson planning, non-verbal communication, classroom management, and instructional delivery were the strongest predictors of teaching practice performance and academic achievement. The study concluded that, although microteaching skills are generally well developed among Business Education students. It was recommended among others, that Business educators should provide continuous, structured, and individualized feedback during microteaching sessions because the findings revealed that students who mastered microteaching skills performed significantly better during teaching practice.

Keywords: Business Education, Microteaching, Teaching Practice Performance, Teacher Preparation.

Introduction

Preparing competent and professionally grounded teachers remains a central priority of teacher education programmes worldwide. In Colleges of Education in Nigeria, teaching practice constitutes one of the most critical components of the preparation, serving as the platform where student-teachers transition from theoretical knowledge to real classroom engagement. Teaching practice exposes prospective teachers to instructional planning, classroom management, lesson delivery, professional responsibilities, and the real dynamics of school environments. Scholars affirmed that effective participation in teaching practice enhances student-teachers' confidence, improves instructional competence, and strengthens their readiness for full-time classroom work (Olusanya, 2020 & Enama, 2021). However, the quality of performance demonstrated during teaching practice is strongly influenced by the level of pedagogical skills student-teachers possess before entering the classroom.

One of the most influential preparatory strategies in teacher education is **microteaching**. Microteaching offers student-teachers the opportunity to rehearse teaching skills under controlled, supervised, and simplified conditions. It reduces the complexities of a full classroom by limiting the number of learners, duration of the lesson and instructional scope, allowing trainees to focus on specific teaching skills such as lesson introduction, questioning, explanation, reinforcement, and evaluation (Onah et al, 2023, Tadese, Yeshaneh & Mulu, 2022). Research has shown that microteaching significantly improves the professional competence of pre-service teachers by providing repeated practice, constructive feedback, and opportunities for correction and refinement of teaching behaviours (Ojo, 2023 & Agogo et al, 2020). In Business Education programmes where effective communication, demonstration, and practical engagement are crucial, microteaching is particularly important for shaping students' instructional competence (Olusanya, 2020).

This study was anchored on the theory of operant conditioning, which was developed by B. F. Skinner in the mid-20th century. This learning paradigm posits that behaviors are influenced by the consequences that follow them, emphasizing reinforcement and punishment as key mechanism for behavior modification. In microteaching, operant conditioning theory can be applied in reinforcing instructional effectiveness and student-engagement.

Despite the acknowledged relevance of microteaching, concerns persist regarding the extent to which microteaching skills translate into excellent teaching practice performance among Business Education students in colleges of education in Southwest Nigeria. Several challenges continue to undermine teaching practice experiences in Nigerian institutions, including excessive workload, inadequate facilities, insufficient supervision, communication gaps between training institutions and cooperating schools, and poor mentoring from cooperating teachers (Ojo, 2023; Maseko, 2022 & Abubakar et al, 2023). These contextual issues raise important questions about whether the microteaching skills acquired by student-teachers can adequately prepare them for the realities of school classrooms.

Empirical evidence suggests that student-teachers who demonstrate strong microteaching skills often perform better during teaching practice, show improved classroom management behaviours and employ more effective teaching strategies (Olusanya, 2020 & Ojo, 2021). However, there is limited research focusing specifically on **Business Education students**, despite the unique skill demands of the discipline and its importance in developing human capital for entrepreneurship, office technology, and business management sectors (Kren-Ikidi, 2020). Moreover, there is a research gap on how microteaching competencies predict teaching practice performance within Colleges of Education in Southwest Nigeria a region with diverse educational environments and a high concentration of teacher-training institutions (Kamoru et al, 2021).

Onah et al (2023) investigated the influence of microteaching on student performance in Teaching practice exercise in Orumna Local Government Area of Anambra State. The population of the study comprised all the final year NCE students of Federal College of Education (Technical) Umunze who went for the 202/2021 teaching practice exercise after the microteaching. The sample for the study included 327 student-teachers while a structured questionnaire was used to gather data. Findings from the study revealed that micro teaching helps students-teachers to overcome stage fright, manage their classes very well improve classroom communication among others.

In another study, Ojo (2023) examined the perceived influence of micro-teaching skills on student-teachers' performance in teaching practice in Colleges of Education in Kwara state. The study answered two research questions and tested two null hypotheses in line with the state objectives. The

large population of the study comprised 904 NCE III (2021/2022), Business Education students in College of Education in Kwara state. Simple random sampling Techniques was used to selected 417 NCE III students. Data were collected using a modified student-teacher assessment form and a self-designed questionnaire titled, “Perceived Influenced of micro-teaching skills on Teachers performance in Teaching practice in College of Education (PIMSSPTPCE). Findings revealed that micro-teaching skills predict teaching practice performance to a moderate extent.

The study sought to provide empirical insight into how specific microteaching skills contribute to the quality of student-teachers’ performance during teaching practice. Understanding this relationship is essential for strengthening teacher preparation programmes, improving instructional effectiveness, and ensuring that Business Education graduates are adequately equipped for classroom practice and future professional roles. Therefore, this study examined microteaching skills as determinants of teaching practice performance among Business Education students in colleges of education in Southwest Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The preparation of competent teachers remains a major concern in Nigeria’s teacher education system. Teaching practice is expected to provide pre-service teachers with meaningful opportunities to apply pedagogical theories in real classroom situations. However, observations and previous studies have shown that many pre-service teachers continue to struggle with key instructional competencies, including lesson planning, content delivery, classroom management, communication skills, and time management (Olusanya, 2020; Ojo, 2023; Olusanya & Ademiluyi, 2022 & Balalerishma (2022), Abubakar & Mohammed, (2023). These challenges weaken their confidence and often result in poor teaching practice performance.

Microteaching has been widely recognized as an effective strategy for improving instructional skills among pre-service teachers. It offers a controlled and supportive environment where trainees can practice specific teaching behaviors, receive feedback, and make necessary adjustments before engaging with real learners. Research suggests that structured microteaching experiences can improve teaching practice performance and enhance academic achievement by closing the gap between theory and practice (Abubakar et al, 2023; Mohammed & Yusuf, 2022; Berad, 2022).

Despite these benefits, the effectiveness of microteaching is influenced by the availability of instructional resources, the quality of supervision, and the commitment of institutions to practical skill development. The researcher also observed that many Business Education students in colleges of education treat microteaching lectures and examinations with levity, which negatively affects their preparedness for full teaching practice (Afriani, 2017 & Magenthiran, 2023). Given the central role of Business Education in developing future educators equipped with pedagogical skills, it is necessary to investigate how microteaching contributes to teaching practice performance and academic achievement. Despite widespread use of microteaching empirical evidence on its predictive strength in Business Education remain exclusive. Therefore, the problem of this study centers on the extent to which microteaching skills predict teaching practice performance among Business Education students in colleges of education in Southwest Nigeria. Addressing this gap is essential for strengthening teacher preparation and ensuring that graduates are equipped for the instructional demands of contemporary classrooms.

Objectives of the Study

The study examined microteaching skills as predictors of teaching practice performance among business education students in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria. The objectives were to:

1. examine the influence of microteaching skills on teaching practice performance among Business Education students in Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria.
2. determine the extent to which microteaching skills predict Business Education students' teaching practice performance.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. How do microteaching skills influence teaching practice performance of Business Education students in Colleges of Education in Southwest Nigeria?
- ii. To what extent do microteaching skills predict Business Education students' teaching practice performance?

Research Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between microteaching skills and teaching practice performance among Business Education students in colleges of education in Southwest Nigeria.

Methodology

The study adopted Correlational research design because the study sought to establish the relationship between microteaching and teaching practice performance. The population of the study consisted of 613 final-year Business Education students from seven Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria. These students had completed microteaching (EDU 223) and teaching practice (EDU 311), making them suitable for examining the relationship between microteaching skills and teaching practice outcomes. The sample for the study consisted of 613 final year Business Education Students in 7 colleges of education in Southwest, Nigeria. Census sampling technique was used to capture the entire students that had completed microteaching and teaching practice exercises because the entire population is manageable.

Primary data were collected using three instruments: A structured questionnaire which comprised two sections- section A for demographic information, Section B contains 20 items that elicited responses on influence of Microteaching skills on teaching practice performance and extent to which micro-teaching skills predict Business Education students teaching practice performance. The 20 items were designed on a 4 point rating scale as follows: Strongly Agree/Very High Extent (4), Agree/High Extent (3), Disagree/Low Extent (2), and Strongly Agree/Very Low Extent (1) Score Sheet: Contained students' scores from EDU 223 (2023/2024 academic session) and Teaching Practice Score Sheet: Contained students' scores from EDU 311 (2024/2025 academic session).

The microteaching and teaching practice score sheets were validated through external moderation. Reliability was determined through a pilot study involving 20 students from Federal Capital Territory (FCT) College of Education, Zuba, Abuja, who were not part of the main study. Reliability coefficients ranged from 0.60 to 0.76 using the Split-Half method and Cronbach Alpha, indicating acceptable

consistency. Data collection involved administering the questionnaire to students with the assistance of trained research assistants, collecting microteaching and teaching practice score sheets from departmental and teaching practice offices under standardized conditions. Participants were provided with clear instructions, and informed consent was obtained before participation.

Descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, means, and standard deviations were used to answer the research questions while inferential statistics, such as Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and Regression Analysis were used to test the hypotheses. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$, using the SPSS version 23.0

Results

Research Question 1: How do microteaching skills influence teaching practice performance of Business Education students in College of education in Southwest Nigeria.

Table 1: Mean responses on the influence of micro-teaching skills on teaching practice performance.

S/N	Item Statements	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	Elimination of state fright	3.50	0.64	Strongly Agreed
2	Improved writing skills on the board	2.62	0.71	Agree
3	Subject-matter mastery	3.19	0.65	Agree
4	Statement of lesson objectives	3.04	0.68	Agree
5	Proper time management	3.11	0.70	Agree
6	Appropriate use of instructional materials	3.01	0.67	Agree
7	Improved questioning Techniques	3.03	0.72	Agree
8	Enhancement of Class control ability	2.88	0.62	Agree
9	Improved communication in the classroom	2.94	0.58	Agree
10	Enhanced instructional delivery	2.79	0.73	Agree

$N = 613$ Decision rule = 2.50, Weighted mean/SD = 3.01/0.67

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Results in Table 1 revealed that respondents agreed that all the items are ways by which micro-teaching skills influence teaching practice performance. This is hinged on the weighted mean of 3.01 which is

higher than the decision rule of 2.50. The weighted standard deviation of 0.67 indicates the homogeneity of the responses.

Research Question Two: Two what extent do micro-teaching skills predict Business Education students teaching practice performance?

Table 2: Mean responses on the extent to which micro teaching skills predict Business Education students teaching practice performance.

S/N	Micro-Teaching Skill	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	Lesson planning	3.51	0.67	Very High Extent
2	Classroom management	3.47	0.69	High Extent
3	Effective use of Instructional Materials	3.38	0.70	High Extent
4	Instruction delivery	3.50	0.68	Very High Extent
5	Questionnaire	3.42	0.70	High Extent
6	Variation	3.33	0.71	High Extent
7	Non-Verbal Communication	3.44	0.69	High Extent
8	Reinforcement	3.39	0.70	High Extent
9	Time Management	3.44	0.68	High Extent
10	White marker board Writing Skill	3.42	0.70	High Extent

N= 613, Decision, rule = 2.50, weighted mean (SD) = 3.42/0.69

Source: Field Survey, 2026.

Results in Table 2 indicated that micro teaching skills predict Business Education students teaching practice performance to a high extent. This is predicated or the weighted mean (3.421) which is higher than the decision rule (2.50). The weighted standard deviation implies that the responses are homogeneous.

Hypothesis One (H₀₁): *There is no significant relationship between microteaching skills and teaching practice performance.*

Table 3: Linear Regression Analysis on Relationship between Microteaching Skills and Teaching Practice Performance of Business Education Students in College of Education.

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	T	P
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	B. Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant) (Independent)	9.195 0.315		0.082	0.224
Microteaching Skills		-0.726		
	-0.014 0.265		0.749*	0.291**

R = 0.726 r² = 0.672 Adjusted r² = 0.652, p = 0.026

Dependent variable: Teaching Practice Performance

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 3 shows the relationship between Microteaching skills and teaching Practice Performance. The result shows positive correlation between Microteaching skills and teaching Practice Performance. The result shows positive correlation between microteaching skills and teaching practice performance of Business Education Students (R=0.726). The results equally reveals that a significant relationship exists between microteaching skills and teaching practice performance. (r² =0.672, p = 0.026). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that microteaching skills have significance relationship with teaching practice performance

Discussion

The findings of this study provide valuable insight into the relationship between microteaching skills and teaching practice performance among Business Education students in Colleges of Education in Southwest Nigeria. Overall, the results suggested that students actively applied microteaching skills during teaching practice, and these skills contributed meaningfully to their performance outcomes. Results from research question one and Table 1 revealed that micro teaching skills influenced Business Education Students teaching practice performance, in the aspects of proper time management, appropriate use of instructional materials and enhanced classroom communication among others. These findings supported the findings of Onah et al (2023), that micro-teaching helps students-teachings to overcome stage fright, manage their classes very, well and improve classroom communicating.

In response to research question Two, Table 2 showed that micro-teaching skill predicted Business Education students teaching practice performance to a high extent. These findings buttressed the findings of Ojo (2023) that micro teaching skills predicted teaching practice performance to a moderate extent.

It was hypothesized that there is no significant relationship between microteaching skills and teaching practice performance among Business Education Students in Colleges of Education, Southwest Nigeria, thus findings in Table 3 showed that micro teaching skills had a significant relationship with teaching practice performance of Business Education Students in Colleges of Education in Southwest Nigeria. This finding corroborated the findings of Olusanya and Ademiluyi (2022) that there was significant relationship between microteaching scores and teaching practice scores of Business Education students in Federal College of Education, Abeokuta.

Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that microteaching skills are critical predictors of teaching practice performance among Business Education students in Colleges of Education in Southwest Nigeria. The findings of this study revealed that micro teaching skills positively and significantly influenced teaching practice performance, which, in turn, enhanced students' academic achievement. The implication of this study is that microteaching is not merely a preparatory exercise but a vital component of professional development that equips student-teachers with the practical and cognitive skills necessary for effective classroom instruction. Consequently, the study underscores the importance of structured microteaching experiences, targeted skill development, and supportive supervision in ensuring that Business Education students are well-prepared to meet the instructional demands of contemporary classrooms. However the study was limited to Business Education students alone, through the findings can be useful to scholars in others fields of education.

Recommendations

1. Since the study found a strong relationship between microteaching skills and teaching practice performance, Colleges of Education should strengthen the delivery of microteaching by

ensuring that students receive consistent, hands-on practice in core skills such as lesson planning, classroom management, questioning techniques, evaluation skills, and instructional delivery before going for teaching practice.

2. Stakeholders in Business Education should ensure that ICT is integrated in microteaching curriculum and ensure that micro teaching is given a strong footing in the curriculum view.
3. There should be regular in-service training for micro-teaching and teaching practice supervisors. such training can be organized by the regulatory agencies such as NUC and NCCE.

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